

**Advantages and possibilities of developing independent work of students in
non-philological higher educational institutions focused on social and
humanities through distance education**

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Annotation

In this article, the role of remote environment in the development of independent work of students of non-philological higher education in socio-humanities and the improvement of pedagogical and didactic design technology for the purpose of its effective use was highlighted. At the same time, one of the priority tasks of reforming the education system, improving it, and increasing the quality level is the improvement of personnel level, the experimental introduction of new scientific ideas, modern approaches and methods to the education system, and the elimination of their problems.

Key words and concepts: distance education, independent educational activity, pedagogical and didactic design, professional content, digital economy.

**Преимущества и возможности развития самостоятельной работы
студентов нефилологических вузов социально-гуманитарного профиля
посредством дистанционного образования**

Аннотация

В данной статье освещено совершенствование технологии педагогического и дидактического проектирования с целью эффективного использования инструмента дистанционного обучения в развитии самостоятельной учебной деятельности студентов по предметам английского языка нефилологического вуза по социальным и гуманитарным наукам. При этом одна из приоритетных задач реформирования системы образования, ее совершенствования и повышения уровня качества находит свое отражение в повышении уровня кадров, экспериментальном внедрении в систему образования новых научных идей, современных подходов и методов, устранение своих проблем.

Ключевые слова и понятия: дистанционное обучение, самостоятельная учебная деятельность, педагогико-дидактическое проектирование, профессиональный контент, цифровая экономика.

Reforming the education system in our republic, improving it, and raising the quality level is one of the priority tasks, to raise the level of personnel, to introduce new scientific ideas, modern approaches and methods to the educational system, to introduce training on the basis of advanced programs with a high degree of complexity, changing labor it requires the training of specialists in accordance with the demand of the market, bringing them to the level of a qualified mature person who can actively participate in the innovative digital economy and have social skills who can ensure their standard of living and the well-being of the population.

Today's real situation encourages us to follow the path of developed countries and reach them faster. This requires the activation of the electronic information system in the field of education, the deep acquisition of knowledge in the field of advanced modern information and communication, Internet and digital technologies, using the experiences of the world's leading educational institutions. Therefore, continuous improvement of literacy in the use of innovative technologies in all layers of our society has become not only a need, but also a necessity today.

Digital economy (Digital Economy) is an economy conducted with the help of digital communications and information technologies, in which modern scientific approaches and innovations are of priority, and the development of industries with high scientific capacity is envisaged. This term was first used in 1995 by Nicholas Negroponte, a computer scientist at the University of Massachusetts, in the context of "a metaphor for the transition from the movement of atoms to the movement of bits." Today, this term is used by politicians, economists, journalists, and businessmen all over the world [1].

The introduction of the digital economy into the field of education itself has raised questions about what digital education is, why it is needed, and how it can be implemented. Digital education is the demand of the 21st century, and our adaptation from previous centuries means the transition from traditional books, paper and pencil to new age digital technologies and artificial intelligence. Our traditional paper and pencils have been replaced by smart phones, tablets, computers of various sizes, which are smart technologies today, and digitization of education has become the need of the hour. Today's young people cannot imagine their life without these technical tools. The goal of digitalization of education also requires the preparation

of educated young people with high intellect who can adapt to the rapid changes in the global world and the rapidly growing flow of innovations.

It seems that, if we turn to international practice, the digital economy is rapidly penetrating every aspect of life, in particular, health, science and education, construction, energy, agriculture and water management, transport, geology, cadastre, archive and other fields, and each of them has its own giving high results. The world experience shows that the transition to the digital economy is developing at a rapid pace:

- that as a result of the acceleration of scientific and technical progress, the need to obtain higher education has arisen in mass;
- due to the need of employees employed in modern industries and service sectors to regularly update their knowledge and skills, the nature of continuity in education is emerging;
- as a result of the development of information and communication technologies, the opportunities for distance education are expanding;
- as a result of digitization of the most influential textbooks, manuals, lectures of famous scientists and experts in their field, opportunities for independent acquisition of knowledge have arisen;
- it is explained by the elimination of territorial and time barriers in education, i.e., the emergence of opportunities for distance learning, independent study of subjects based on a personal agenda, even in prestigious universities abroad [2].

This shows that the rapid implementation of the integration process between the education system and the digital economy in our country and the transition to the system of flexibility in education for the digitization of the system, the popularization of the distance education system among students and teachers are

directly connected with the gradual improvement of the main elements of distance education [3]. Like all educational systems, the distance learning system has its own structural goals, content, methods, tools and organizational forms[4]. In the sources, it can be seen that the concept of "distance education" is defined as follows:

– education focused on the use of educational resources based on traditional and innovative forms, methods, tools in the provision of educational services, distribution and delivery of educational products using information and communication tools (video, audio, computer, multimedia, radio, television, etc.) [5];

– form of education based on information and telecommunication technologies such as part-time and full-time education, including the best traditional and innovative methods, teaching tools and forms;

– an educational system based on new information technologies, telecommunication technologies and technical means, providing the learner with educational conditions and communication with the teacher based on certain standards and educational laws, and requiring the student to engage more independently. In this case, the learning process does not depend on the time and place of the learner:

– an educational complex based on distance learning information sharing tools, the teacher provides educational services to all strata of the population and foreign students with the help of a special information environment.

Distance education saves the cost and time of attending educational institutions, during which time students have the opportunity to acquire additional new knowledge from other sources, and it creates conditions for the use of all educational resources through the Internet and for everyone to communicate with each other or with the teacher.

Communication with the pedagogue from a distance usually takes place between the pedagogue and the students, the results of the tasks completed by the students are only in the student's personal office. It is this situation that helps students to overcome shyness and fear of being underestimated in front of many. Only the student will be aware of any shortcoming or opinions expressed by the pedagogue, and conditions will be created for him to work harder on himself and eliminate his shortcomings. There are also specific principles of distance education, and these principles include a number of objective tasks.

In fact, in today's situation, when the world recognizes the conveniences and advantages of the distance education system, it is the responsible task of today's innovative pedagogues to be able to use it effectively, to study all its possibilities and put it into practice.

In short, the effectiveness of distance education depends on the correct presentation of educational materials, but until today, the issue of pedagogical and didactic design of organizing students' independent work with the help of distance learning technologies has not been sufficiently grounded in theory, in particular, in non-philological fields, the independent work of students in a foreign language can be done remotely management, their acceptance and evaluation forms have not been developed, one of the urgent and problematic issues of today. Independent work of students is an integral part of the educational process, and it is the work that students do individually without the direct participation or indirect management of the teacher. The high level of development of information and communication technologies and the Internet creates a unique innovative environment for teachers and students, and in this global information environment, it is becoming a requirement of the time to control the independent learning activities of students and

encourage them to be independent researchers. It should be noted that in higher education institutions of all countries of the world special attention is paid to the independent work of students, but the problems regarding the forms and efficiency of organizing independent work have not yet been fully resolved.

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